

Hybrid peer-reviewed journals and publishing model: Bias or impartiality in editorial policy

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Abstract

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in scientific productivity—an increased number of published original articles, reviews, short communications, case reports, and letters to the editor. In this regard, there is a large number of peer-reviewed journals in all fields of scientific knowledge, including in the field of biomedical sciences. Many studies indicate the existence of so-called journal editorial board bias and acknowledge the difficulty of eliminating it. We present our brief opinion on an important topic such as how publishing policy in some peer-reviewed journals leads to feelings of bias and inequality among authors and how to address this.

Keywords

bias, editorial policy, hybrid journals, impartiality, publishing model

Dear Editor

Publishing is the main method for scientists to share their research and communicate insights to as large a readership as possible. Scientific publishing is an important step in a researcher's career, especially for beginning researchers and PhD students, where publication record is the essential metric tool for judging their career advancement (Glover et al. 2016).

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in scientific production (Kokulu et al. 2019; Gonzalez-Alcaide et al. 2024). Researchers from all regions of the world are increasing their scientific productivity and they are looking

for a field for expression (Li et al. 2024). In addition, a large number of scientific publishers have tangibly increased their portfolio of peer-reviewed journals (Table 1) (Scilit 2025). According to the method of publishing on accepted manuscripts, peer-reviewed journals are divided into three main groups: (1) Open Access; (2) Hybrid; (3) Subscription Access. It is noteworthy that over the last decade, more and more publishers have been stimulating open access journals (Pulverer 2023; Quaiia et al. 2024). This is understandable because open access journals reach a larger readership; the reader has full access to the content of each article, and this leads to opportunities for higher citation. It should be noted that the article processing charges (APCs) in these journals (open

access) are paid by the authors. This leads to financial difficulties for authors from developing countries. In hybrid journals, there are two publishing options: (a) subscription access (the article is available only to readers with a subscription); (b) open access (APCs are paid by the authors, and the article is available to all readers). In subscription-based journals, all articles are available only to readers with a subscription.

The large number of peer-reviewed journals of all kinds allowed scientists to publish their research and share the knowledge gained with the scientific community according to the available capabilities. However, some studies indicate concerns regarding scientific publishing related to several factors, including the inability of some scientists or organizations to cover APCs cost of handling the publication of their works (Bjork and Solomon 2014; Nabyonga-Orem 2022).

Hybrid peer-reviewed journals play an important role in scientific communities. It is suitable for those who can obtain the necessary funding to publish their research and get more visibility (open access option), citations, and influence from their research, as well as for junior or unfunded researchers, especially from low-income (LI) countries and lower middle-income (LMI) countries (Frank et al. 2023).

This opinion is mainly addressed to editors and editorial boards by the hybrid peer-reviewed journals. Latterly, we notice that some of these journals ask the corresponding author at the initial submitting step about the publishing option choice (open access or subscription) they will use in the future (if the manuscript is accepted). We do not discuss this matter from the journal's point of view; perhaps this behavior is an internal regulatory procedure or something like that. However, from the author's point of view, the latter believes that his manuscript will be treated with preference if he pays APCs and chooses the open access option, and vice versa if he chooses the closed publishing (subscription) option. Although this feeling may be illusory, it is widespread among authors from LI/LMI countries (Frank et al. 2023).

Many factors can enhance this feeling, such as the fact that the scientist is at the beginning of his career or the growing idea that publishing in peer-reviewed journals with APCs is much easier than in classical peer-reviewed journals without APCs. Additionally, suppose the journal receives a large number of manuscripts. In that case, it is possible that the selection process in the first review stage does not solely consider the manuscript's quality and suitability for the journal. Instead, the author's choice of publishing model may be a deciding factor in whether the manuscript will enter the review stage (Khezzani, unpublished data). In this regard, some scientists think that simi-

lar manuscripts receive different attitudes, even when they address the same problem, utilize similar materials and methods, and yield similar results and discussions (Khezzani, unpublished data). In addition, scientists from LI/LMI countries think that they are at a disadvantage compared to scientists from upper middle-income (UMI) countries and high-income (HI) countries (Khezzani, unpublished data).

A large number of peer-reviewed journals introduce editorial policies for impartiality and adequate evaluation of submitted manuscripts. However, studies have reported that biased behavior exists among editors and editorial boards and cannot be wholly eliminated in scientific publishing (Matias-Guiu and Garcia-Ramos 2011). In this regard, the behavior mentioned above promotes the feeling of being exposed to bias and discrimination by the journal's editorial boards for authors from LI/LMI countries.

The feeling of bias and inequality can affect scientific production. In this context, Scanff et al. (2021) consider that integrity is an important factor in scientific research, and the journal editorial board is an effective part that guarantees the trustworthiness of the scientific publication process. There is no doubt that peer-reviewed journals do not hesitate to take action to enhance their reputation in the scientific community. Editorial boards make efforts to reduce bias and achieve equity among scientists. In this regard, editors and editorial boards of peer-reviewed journals can observe several ethical rules of work:

- Each submitted manuscript is to be reviewed by two editors.
- Editors to choose as reviewers—scientists from countries with different economic development (for example, one reviewer from LI/LMI country and one reviewer from UMI/HI country).
- The evaluation of the manuscript to include the economic situation in the country (for LI/LMI countries) and the real opportunities for scientific activity in such a country.
- More frequent and larger APC discounts for authors from LI/LMI countries.
- Creation of special issues or supplements to peer-reviewed journals for studies of scientists from LI/LMI countries.

These are some of the steps that can be taken to reduce bias and create equality between scientists from different parts of the world. That is why we think that the matter of asking authors about their nature of publishing option choice

Table 1. Ranking of the largest scientific publishers by number of journals and published articles (for the last year, 2024).

Publisher	Total Journals, n	Open Access Journals, n (%)	Total Articles, n	Open Access Articles, n (%)
Elsevier	2,964	724 (24.4)	962,326	301,321 (31.3)
Springer Nature	2,956	780 (26.3)	528,859	251,943 (47.6)
Taylor & Francis	2,535	359 (14.1)	155,562	54,881 (35.2)
Wiley	1,813	296 (16.3)	292,093	125,808 (43.0)
SAGE Publications	1,295	240 (18.5)	85,789	32,492 (37.8)
Egyptian Knowledge Bank	896	40 (4.4)	46,860	257 (0.5)
Walter de Gruyter GmbH	716	397 (55.4)	30,425	19,341 (63.5)
Wolters Kluwer Health	634	165 (26.0)	93,212	23,768 (25.4)
Oxford University Press	510	137 (26.8)	105,294	66,946 (63.5)
MDPI	455	454 (99.7)	241,656	241,655 (99.9)

in hybrid peer-reviewed journals is a premature question (when the author submits his manuscript). In such cases, the sensible alternative is to ask the author about the publication option (open access or subscription) once the peer-reviewed process has been successfully completed. This approach can be applied to most hybrid peer-reviewed journals.

In conclusion, this opinion can help editors and editorial boards of hybrid peer-reviewed journals to reduce the risk of bias and uphold the evaluation of manuscripts based solely on their scholarly merit. This approach is in line with the principles of academic integrity and fosters a scholarly environment that is more inclusive and equitable. Editors and editorial boards of hybrid peer-reviewed journals face many problems. That is why their solution requires a discussion in the scientific community in order to make the most adequate decisions.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist. The funders had no role in the design of this manuscript, in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the manuscript.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

All authors made a significant contribution to the manuscript, whether that is in the conception, design, execution, or all these areas; took part in drafting, revising, or critically reviewing the manuscript; gave final approval of the version to be published; agreed on the journal to which the article has been submitted; and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.